

Studies on Adsorption of Humic Acid by Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ Hydroxide Gels

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Adsorption of humic acids by Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ hydroxide gels were studied. Modified Langmuir adsorption equation was found to be applicable and the adsorption was pH dependent.

IRON and aluminium are present as their hydroxide gels or as sols in soil¹. So there is a possibility of interaction of such hydroxide gels with soil 0.M in soil. With this idea, an attempt has been made to find out the nature of interaction of these species with soil 0.M. As gels are supposed to form adsorption type of complexes with metals², attempt has been made to study whether Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ gels also form such types of complexes with HA/FA and if so whether Langmuir equation is applicable in such system. As adsorption of Zn by hydrated Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ is found to be pH dependent^{3,4}, effect of pH on the adsorption has also been studied.

The Langmuir equation used in the present study is slightly modified⁵ from the original one as the adsorption takes place in solution. The modified equation is

$$\frac{c}{x/m} = \frac{1}{bk} + \frac{c}{k} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where c, is the concentration of the adsorbate in solution, k is the maximum adsorption capacity, x/m is the amount of adsorbate, adsorbed per unit amount of adsorbent and b is a Langmuir constant related to the adsorption energy.

Experimental

Preparation of Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ hydroxide gels: Gels were prepared by the rapid (about 15 mins) neutralisation of Fe(NO₃)₃ (A. R.) solutions with NaOH to pH 7. After the suspensions had been maintained at pH 7 for about one hour, the suspensions were dialysed to free from excess electrolyte and made upto the appropriate volume, so that the final concentration in suspensions was 0.33 M with respect to Fe/Al.

Humic acids used in the investigation were extracted and fractionated from a pond sediment (Bigra, Burdwan, West Bengal) in the usual way as reported earlier⁶. The average molecular weights of HA and FA as measured by electrometric method⁹ have been found to be 2000 and 1250 respectively.

Different sets of mixtures of HA/FA and Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ gels were prepared by varying the amount of HA/FA. The mixtures were shaken for 5-6 hours

and kept for 24 hours for equilibration at 30° temperature and the pH of the solutions were measured. The adsorption complexes were centrifuged and the amounts of unadsorbed 0.M were determined by the oxidation method of Walkley and Black⁷. The zero point charges (zpc) of the gels were determined according to the procedure adopted by Kinniburgh *et al*⁸ (Fig. 1). Different sets of mixtures of HA/FA and Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ gels were adjusted at different pH's some below zpc, some at zpc and some above zpc. The adsorption complexes thus prepared were similarly centrifuged and the amount of unadsorbed 0.M were determined in the centrifugates as above. The curves of n (where n = x/m) vs pH (Fig. 2) and also c/n vs c (Fig. 3) were drawn where c is the concentration in m gm of 0.M and x/m is the amount of 0.M adsorbed in m gm per gram of gel. When c is very small, the equation(1) reduces to the form n = kbc. Hence from the plot of n vs c (Fig. 4), kb was obtained from the slope. Again k was obtained from the plot of c/n vs c using the equation c/n = 1/bk + c/k (Fig. 3). Now from kb and k, the value of b was evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The zpc for Fe⁺³ and Al⁺³ gels are found to be 8.0 and 9.2 respectively. The observed zpc for Fe⁺³/Al⁺³ gel is reasonably close to those reported

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

by Kinniburg⁹. The curve for the Al³⁺ gel is peculiar in that it lacks symmetry and crosses $pH=0$ line twice. The first crossover point at $pH=9.2$ is thought to be reasonably close to the true zpc^8 and recent determination of isoelectric point of aluminium hydroxide in salt solution show this in $pH 9-9.2^{10}$. The reason for the upward turn in the curve is not certain. Aluminium gel has a tendency to get hydrolysed as $Al(OH)_2^+$, possibly that shifts the pH towards higher side and thus there is depression in the pH curve.

The graph of concentration of 0.1M adsorbed by the gels against pH (Fig. 2) shows that adsorption does not depend much on zpc values. It is, however, clear that rate of adsorption is increased with pH increase but the magnitude of increase was higher at pH below zpc than at pH above it. The variation in the amount of adsorption with pH also conforms to the observation made by Kalbasi *et al*⁸ for adsorption of zinc by iron and aluminium oxides.

The plot of $c/x/m$ of 0.1M against concentration (c) of gels (Fig. 3) shows straight lines over the concentration range studied. The plot is commonly curvilinear which is probably due to less amount of adsorption of ions resulting from the very small dissociation of HA/FA. However, it is noted from the plot that the Langmuir equation is applicable for such system at low equilibrium concentration level. The values of b from Table 1 show that the

TABLE 1—LANGMUIR'S COEFFICIENTS AT 80°

	b ml/g	k mg/g
HA-Fe ³⁺ gel	0.95	1.66
HA-Al ³⁺ gel	0.37	1.83
FA-Fe ³⁺ gel	0.35	1.11
FA-Al ³⁺ gel	0.48	0.83

amounts of 0.1M adsorbed by Fe³⁺/Al³⁺ gel are very low. The very low k values in all the cases indicate relatively weak bonding energy involved in adsorption. The adsorption is thus considered to be physical in nature.

References

1. M. M. KONONOVA, *Soil Organic Matter*, Pergamon Press (1961).
2. R. O. JAMES and T. W. HEALY, *J. Coll. Interface Sci.*, 1972, 40, 65.
3. M. KALBASI, G. J. RAOZ and RUDGER L. A. LOEWEN, *Soil Sci.*, 1978, 125, 146.
4. L. M. SHUMAN, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1977, 41, 703.
5. D. H. ROBERT and E. B. DALE, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1977, 41, 883.
6. M. ADHIKARI and G. C. HAZRA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 522.
7. M. L. JACKSON, *Soil Chemical Analysis*, 1967, p. 219.
8. D. G. KINNIBURG, J. K. SYERS and M. L. JACKSON, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1975, 39, 464.
9. M. ADHIKARI, K. K. CHAKRABARTI and G. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 489.
10. R. S. ALWITH, *J. Coll. Interface Sci.*, 1972, 40, 195.